

МЕДИЧНА ОСВІТА

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PROFESSIONAL GROWTH OF A FUTURE TEACHER THROUGH THE PRISM OF HIS VALUE SELF-DETERMINATION

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Abstract. The article focuses on the need to develop a conscious approach to studying the problem of value self-determination. In modern socio-economic and cultural-historical conditions of Ukraine, there is polyphony and uncertainty of spiritual and moral orientations of society, which determines increased requirements for the ability of a future specialist to carry out a conscious, responsible search for new meanings of professional activity, to self-define in the context of historical, cultural, social and professional realities, as well as to rethink and transform his own life and professional experience.

The purpose of this study is a theoretical analysis of the essence of value self-determination in the professional activity of a future teacher, to identify its components and conditions that influence this process.

Methodologically, the study is based on a systemic approach, which involves a comprehensive analysis of both external and internal factors that form the value orientations of the individual. The focus is on value self-determination as a stimulus for development and the ability to consciously and responsibly choose the values and goals of pedagogical activity, as well as to design a life and professional path.

The article examines the value nature of self-determination, which is a manifestation of internal psychological freedom and involves a choice from available alternatives. Particular attention is paid to the process of forming personal and professional values, which form the basis of the formation of the personality of a future teacher. The principles of organizing an educational space aimed at realizing the social functioning of values and the variability of professional value orientations are determined.

It is proven that the key condition for the strategic development of the professional life of a future teacher is a formed system of values, which determines the choice of both life and professional goals. The combination of external and internal factors of value self-determination contributes to qualitative changes in the personality, which is an important component of professional development.

The value self-determination of a future teacher is a key process of his personal and professional formation. It is formed under the influence of both external socio-economic conditions and internal psychological factors, in particular the system of value orientations and motives. Effective value self-determination contributes to the formation of a holistic worldview, awareness of one's place in the professional sphere and responsible choice of pedagogical strategy. Therefore, the modern system of professional training of teachers should be aimed at supporting and developing this process, creating conditions for a harmonious combination of personal values with professional ones, which ultimately ensures high quality of pedagogical activity and psychological well-being of both teachers themselves and their students.

Keywords: future teacher, values, value orientations, value self-determination, personal self-determination, professional self-determination, professional values, professional development, pedagogical activity.

Introduction. In the modern socio-economic and cultural-historical conditions of Ukraine, there is a polyphony and uncertainty of the spiritual and moral orientations of society, which determines the increased requirements for the ability of a future specialist to carry out a conscious, responsible search for new meanings of professional activity, to self-define in the context of historical, cultural, social and professional realities, as well as to rethink and transform his own life and professional experience. Value orientations are a key factor in choosing a professional trajectory and developing the personality of a future teacher. Although they are formed under the influence of dominant social values and an influential educational environment,

they are not exclusively a product of external influences. The personality shows selectivity towards informational, socio-cultural and professional stimuli, which indicates its active position in the process of value self-determination. Therefore, the system of value orientations is formed as a result of the interaction between social guidelines, educational values and the personal activity of the subject.

The professional growth of a future teacher directly depends on his or her value orientations, individual and personal characteristics, as well as readiness for creative search in the conditions of educational innovations. It is these factors that determine the quality of pedagogical interaction and the effectiveness of the educational process.

In this regard, the formation of a new style of professional activity that meets the challenges of modern education requires the actualization of the issues of value self-determination.

Ignoring the value dimension of professionalization by a future teacher leads to a disruption of harmony in pedagogical interaction, a decrease in the level of professional readiness and the quality of pedagogical activity in general.

Therefore, in today's conditions, there is an urgent need for an in-depth theoretical and methodological analysis and empirical research of the phenomenon of value self-determination of a future teacher. After all, it is in the process of professionalization that a person comprehends his or her own worldview, determines life guidelines and gives meaning to his or her own existence.

Research justification. The issue of value self-determination of a future teacher has long attracted the attention of scientists from various fields of knowledge, which indicates its constant relevance in the context of personal and professional development. The methodological foundations of the study of the phenomenon of self-determination were considered within the framework of the broader problem of determination, in particular as the relationship between external factors and internal conditions of personality development. The above-mentioned position is reflected in the statement: "...any determination is necessary as determination by others, external, as well as self-determination..." [1, p. 67]. In this aspect, self-determination is interpreted as a form of self-determination, characterized by active subjective assimilation and transformation of external influences through the prism of internal psychological mechanisms. Thus, self-determination appears not only as a process, but also as a result of the individual acquiring his own identity, the formation of a personality as a unique individuality that occupies a clearly defined worldview position. This phenomenon can be summarized by the catchphrase: "Search for yourself until you find yourself."

Despite numerous studies, at the present stage the content characteristics and regularities of value self-determination as a phenomenon of personal development have not yet been finally determined. Its theoretical understanding remains a subject of interest not only in philosophy and sociology, but also in psychological and pedagogical sciences.

In philosophical discourse, self-determination is considered in the context of ontological and epistemological problems – in particular, the meaning of life, free will, the nature of consciousness and the relationship between personality and society. The works of J.-J. Rousseau, I. Kant, A. Schopenhauer, F. Nietzsche, G. Schulz, etc. are devoted to this issue.

The sociological approach interprets self-determination as a process of social identification of a generation as a whole, which encompasses its integration into social structures and social practices (A. Arvanitis, L. M. Daniels, L. Dong, T. L. Durksen, S. Kaldi, G.-M. M. Sappa, etc.).

The growing attention to the problem of value

self-determination of future teachers in the modern educational environment has led to the intensification of scientific research among Ukrainian psychologists. In particular, a significant contribution to the study of this phenomenon was made by I. D. Bekh, S. I. Bilozerska, L. V. Dolynska, N. I. Ivantsev, Z. S. Karpenko, S. D. Maksymenko, N. P. Maksymchuk, O. B. Martyniuk, G. K. Radchuk, M. V. Savchyn, A. V. Furman, S. V. Yaremchuk and others.

The analysis of scientific positions allows us to interpret value self-determination as a leading new formation of student age, which is formed as a result of the integration of personal experience, pedagogical interaction and professionalization. In this context, the process of assimilation and selection of values occurs in close connection with the development of the professional identity of the future teacher.

In psychological science, one of the most general approaches to interpreting the phenomenon of self-determination is its understanding as the ability of an individual to independently comprehend his own life, conscious regulation of life activities in accordance with his own value orientations, in particular in the context of the professional development of a future teacher [6]. Self-determination is also interpreted as the process of self-positioning in relation to general cultural values, which ensures the formation and justification of a life position [9], or as the highest level of life choice, which implies the ability of an individual to be a full-fledged subject of his own existence [11].

Numerous modern studies devoted to value self-determination are based on the humanistic approach of A. Maslow, who introduced the concept of professional development and the central phenomenon for it - self-actualization, which is understood as the desire of an individual for self-development, the realization of one's own potential through activity. In his concept, the concepts of self-actualization and self-realization are closest to self-determination [17].

From the position of V. Dryapika, self-determination of an individual is carried out through the process of forming value orientations, which appear as a relatively stable system of meaningful life attitudes that determine the integrative orientation of the individual. These orientations are manifested in the ability to holistically comprehend and emotionally experience reality, readiness for evaluative activity and motivation for professional self-realization [5].

Undoubtedly, the social significance of the value orientations of a future teacher acquires special importance in the context of the formation of his value world, which provides a professional influence on the upbringing of moral and value orientations in students. Pedagogical activity belongs to the sphere of «value-creative» professions, within which the profession itself appears as an internal value that determines the vector of life, personal and professional self-determination, directs the self-realization and self-development of the future specialist.

Despite the fact that there is no unified system for classifying the value orientations of a future teacher in the scientific discourse, most researchers note that the key

feature of value self-determination in adolescence is the formation of a systemic relationship between value orientations, attitudes and the process of becoming a mature personality [3; 6; 10; 12].

Self-determination is a key mechanism for the formation of personal maturity of students of pedagogical institutions of higher education, which is manifested in the conscious choice of one's own position in the system of socio-professional relations. The need of a future teacher to realize his value potential testifies to his desire to form an autonomous position in the structure of interpersonal, informational, emotional and professional relations [2]. The specified process is closely connected with self-knowledge and the formation of a personal attitude not only to the surrounding reality, but also to oneself, one's capabilities, abilities, which implies a conscious correlation of personal potential with the requirements of the chosen professional activity [7].

The quality of functioning of a modern higher education institution directly depends on the level of professional training of the student, his motivational readiness for pedagogical activity, the desire for self-realization in the chosen profession. Educational transformations taking place within the framework of the reform of the domestic educational system lead to a reorientation of the self-determination of the future teacher, which is accompanied by changes in the structure of his personal and professional values. In the context of the modern educational paradigm, an important task is the formation of such an educational environment that will contribute to the implementation of the student's individual educational trajectory, stimulate his self-development, self-organization and conscious construction of a personal life perspective. The axiological core of professional pedagogical education should be represented by a system of basic humanistic values, in particular: Life, Freedom, Responsibility, Faith, Cognition, Spirituality, World Culture, Labor, Communication and Cooperation. Such values are integrated in nature, correspond to the deep meanings of human existence and are directly correlated with the content of professional education.

Scientific research already contains a lot of work devoted to the study of the relationship between value orientations and behavioral strategies of the individual, the interaction of individual value systems with group consciousness, as well as the consideration of the formation of value orientations as one of the key indicators of personal self-determination. The dynamics of value orientations in ontogenesis have also been studied. At the same time, issues related to the process of forming the value self-determination of a future teacher, the factors that determine it, the conditions for its optimization, as well as the peculiarities of the influence of professionalization on the formation of the value structure of the individual remain insufficiently covered. In addition, the essence and hierarchy of the value orientations of a future teacher in the context of the challenges of modern society need to be clarified.

The purpose of the study was to reveal the psychological nature of value self-determination in the context of the

professional activity of a future teacher and to identify the factors that determine its formation.

Presentation of the main material of the study. The peculiarity of the approach to studying the problem of value self-determination of a future teacher lies in the focus on personality development, which involves the analysis of psychological mechanisms of internalization and comprehension of social experience, emotional perception of what has been achieved, as well as how at the stage of personal and professional development a student combines the desired with the possible [4, p. 109].

The process of value self-determination of students of pedagogical higher education institutions is implemented both through the assimilation of the content of academic disciplines focused on the humanitarian aspects of human existence, and through the mastery of educational technologies that stimulate the subject to constant reflection on his own life path. The use of goal-setting mechanisms in educational activities contributes to the transfer of the logic of achieving educational goals to the process of constructing a personal life perspective [16].

Value orientations are the foundation of the process of self-determination both in professionalization and in life in general. They represent a system of social attitudes that are fixed in consciousness and have significance for the individual, determining his behavior, motivation for actions aimed at achieving socially approved ideals and goals.

Regarding the value orientations of the future teacher, N. P. Maksymchuk defines them as social values of a strategic nature that are of key importance for the regulation of behavior and professional activity of the teacher, forming the direction of his needs, motives and interests [10].

In the structure of the teacher's personality, the system of value orientations represents the highest level of adaptation to the social environment, determining the peculiarities of perception of living conditions and style of behavior in the long term. Since the professional activity of a teacher is closely related to basic humanistic values - «child», «development», «life», «mental health» - in a situation of professional self-determination, a person relies on his own system of value orientations. The main components of a person's value self-determination in the pedagogical sphere include: a system of life meanings and goals; the significance of professional activity in the general hierarchy of life priorities; the content of professional values, which includes goals and means of achieving them.

Thus, the system of value orientations of a future teacher, which is formed in the process of professional training in a pedagogical institution of higher education, is oriented towards both personally significant and professionally relevant values. These orientations constitute an essential component of the value component of the formation of the personality of a future teacher. The content of pedagogical activity is determined by the presence of specific motivational determinants, among which the leading ones are the needs for self-realization, self-development, self-improvement and development of the potential of others. At the same time, the relationship between the concepts of "child's personality" and "teacher's profes-

sionalism” is system-forming.

In the context of the formation of value self-determination, the key role is played not only by the presence of a personal system of values (personal self-determination), but also by its effective application for the development of professionally significant orientations that represent professional self-determination.

Personal self-determination involves the formation, actualization and constant updating of the image of the “I” in its various manifestations - professional, personal, spiritual and moral. It has an axiological orientation and provides a purposeful orientation of the individual to the future. As M. Savchyn notes, moral values represent the existential need of the individual to understand life, form the basis of other needs, contribute to self-expression, self-affirmation, disclosure of the uniqueness of the individual and ensure the integrity of its inner world [14, p. 155].

The formation of a system of personal meanings is based on the process of internalization of values [8]. Thanks to this process, stable conscious beliefs, principles, norms of behavior, ideals and personal values arise in young men and women, and the ability to observe and comprehend the phenomena of the surrounding world, self-reflection and understanding of one’s own “I” is also formed. In this case, the development of the personality is determined not so much by the amount of acquired knowledge, but by the willingness to make decisions and act independently in new, non-standard life situations.

Personal self-determination is considered as a process of conscious awareness by the subject of his own inner essence and place in the system of social relations, which has a value-semantic character and is manifested through an active attitude towards himself and the surrounding reality. The ideal of vocational education is to achieve not only a semantic understanding of professional activity, but also an awareness of its personal significance, which is accompanied by the emotional involvement of the subject in the profession. As a result, the value orientations of the personality become authentic professional values.

Professional values are understood as “a system of cognitive formations combined with an emotional-volitional mechanism, an internal reference point of the personality, which stimulates and directs motives, professional actions and deeds, determining the axiological nature of professional activity” [3, p. 64].

Therefore, the process of forming the goals and meanings of professional (pedagogical) activity can be considered the essence of the value self-determination of the future teacher as a subject of educational and professional activity.

This allows us to assert that the educational process should be organized in such a way that within its framework the future specialist could realize the social functioning of values, identify the variability of the values of professional activity and correlate them with cultural norms. This creates conditions for a reflexive assessment of one’s own value concepts and orientations.

In modern conditions, a teacher is faced with unpre-

dictable educational situations that require constant decision-making regarding the priority of certain pedagogical actions, the choice of promising pedagogical technologies and active participation in the process of professional choice. Awareness of the meaning of specific pedagogical actions and the socio-historical significance of pedagogical work as a whole affects the definition of the goal, tasks, content, methods of teaching and upbringing, shapes the nature of the relationship between participants in the pedagogical process and determines the choice of the teacher’s individual professional strategy. In the context of creativity and freedom of action, the level of personal responsibility of the teacher for choosing his own professional strategy increases. Spontaneity and uncertainty in professional behavior give way to a conscious, free and value-based framework of pedagogical activity, the basis of which is the value self-determination of the future teacher.

An important aspect in this process is the positive attitude of the future teacher to the professional and labor sphere, which is formed through the harmonization of intrapersonal and professional needs that cover the entire life and work path of the individual in the process of approaching the values of culture, science and profession.

Content analysis of the key characteristics of value self-determination allows us to consider it as an internal stimulus and the basis of personal development, which requires determining both external and internal conditions for its formation.

The external conditions of value self-determination include the objective socio-economic situation in which professional self-consciousness is formed. This situation is reflected in social and individual consciousness through such aspects as:

- demand for the profession;
- prestige of the profession and motivation for its choice;
- content features of professional activity.

Internal (psychological) conditions include not only the development of the personality, but also the system of its value orientations and motives. The value self-determination of the future teacher is based on such landmarks as truth (cognitive activity), benefit (practical activity), justice (communicative activity), goodness (moral activity), beauty (creative activity), as well as harmony with the world and oneself (spiritual practice).

The combination of external and internal conditions causes qualitative changes in the personality of the student-future teacher. This is manifested in the formation of a holistic value outlook and awareness of one’s place and role in the world. Throughout life, a person is constantly faced with the issues of choosing life landmarks, determining a value attitude to the professional sphere, reflecting on one’s own achievements, and realizing goals and meanings when planning one’s professional future in pedagogy.

In our opinion, the system of professional training of future teachers today should be aimed at creating conditions for the realization of their life prospects related to their future profession, through the formation of value orientations that correspond to professional activity.

So, the value self-determination of an individual is the process of searching for the meaning, goals and resources of one's own life in educational space and time. This process causes qualitative changes in the individual through the formation of a holistic view of the world and understanding of one's place in it. It is associated with the choice of one's own position by the future teacher, the formation of self-awareness, which generates the need to know oneself as a unique individual, to define one's own «I». In the process of professional formation, the value concepts of the individual are supplemented, refined and transformed. They serve as the basis for self-regulation of behavior, self-education, reflection, as well as planning actions aimed at preserving the mental health and psychological well-being of children, taking into account one's own resources.

Conclusion. Value self-determination of a future teacher is a key process of his personal and professional development. It is formed under the influence of both external socio-economic conditions and internal psychological factors, in particular the system of value orientations and motives. Effective value self-determination contributes to the formation of a holistic worldview, awareness of one's place in the professional sphere and responsible choice of pedagogical strategy. Therefore, the modern system of professional training of teachers should be aimed

at supporting and developing this process, creating conditions for a harmonious combination of personal values with professional ones, which ultimately ensures high quality of pedagogical activity and psychological well-being of both teachers themselves and their students.

Prospects for further research in the field of value self-determination of future teachers can be aimed, firstly, at studying the influence of various educational technologies and innovative methods on the formation of value orientations of students of pedagogical specialties. This will allow developing effective approaches to the development of professionally important values; secondly, studying the relationship between value self-determination and the level of psychological well-being of students, as well as their ability to withstand stress in the conditions of modern educational activity. These areas will help to better understand the essence of value self-determination, improve the system of teacher training and improve the quality of the educational process.

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ПРОФЕСІЙНЕ ЗРОСТАННЯ МАЙБУТНЬОГО ВЧИТЕЛЯ КРИЗЬ ПРИЗМУ ЙОГО ЦІННІСНОГО САМОВИЗНАЧЕННЯ

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Резюме. У статті акцентовано увагу на необхідності розробки свідомого підходу до дослідження проблеми ціннісного самовизначення. У сучасних соціально-економічних та культурно-історичних умовах України спостерігається поліфонія й невизначеність духовно-моральних орієнтирів суспільства, що зумовлює підвищені вимоги до здатності майбутнього фахівця здійснювати усвідомлений, відповідальний пошук нових смислів професійної діяльності, необхідність самовизначення в контексті історичних, культурних, соціальних та професійних реалій, а також важливість переосмислення й трансформування власного життєвого і професійного досвіду.

Метою даного дослідження є теоретичний аналіз сутності ціннісного самовизначення у професійній діяльності майбутнього педагога, виявлення його складових та умов, що впливають на цей процес.

Методологічно дослідження базується на системному підході, що передбачає комплексний аналіз як зовнішніх, так і внутрішніх чинників, які формують ціннісні орієнтації особистості. У центрі уваги перебуває ціннісне самовизначення як стимул розвитку та здатність свідомо й відповідально здійснювати вибір цінностей і цілей педагогічної діяльності, а також проектувати життєвий і професійний шлях.

У статті розглядається ціннісна природа самовизначення, яка виступає проявом внутрішньої психологічної свободи та допускає вибір із наявних альтернатив. Особливу увагу приділено процесу формування особистісно-професійних цінностей, що становлять основу становлення особистості майбутнього вчителя. Визначено принципи організації освітнього простору, спрямованого на усвідомлення соціального функціонування цінностей і варіативності професійних ціннісних орієнтацій.

Доведено, що ключовою умовою стратегічного розвитку професійного життя майбутнього педагога є сформована система цінностей, яка визначає вибір як життєвих, так і професійних цілей. Поєднання зовнішніх і внутрішніх факторів ціннісного самовизначення сприяє якісним змінам у особистості, що є важливою складовою професійного розвитку.

Ціннісне самовизначення майбутнього вчителя є ключовим процесом його особистісного та професійного становлення. Воно формується під впливом як зовнішніх соціально-економічних умов, так і внутрішніх психологічних факторів, зокрема системи ціннісних орієнтацій і мотивів. Ефективне ціннісне самовизначення сприяє формуванню цілісного світогляду, усвідомленню свого місця у професійній сфері та відповідальному вибору педагогічної стратегії. Тому сучасна система професійної підготовки педагогів має бути спрямована на підтримку і розвиток цього процесу, створюючи умови для гармонійного поєднання особистісних цінностей із професійними, що в кінцевому результаті забезпечує високу якість педагогічної діяльності та психологічне благополуччя як

самих педагогів, так і їхніх учнів.

Ключові слова: майбутній педагог, цінності, ціннісні орієнтації, ціннісне самовизначення, особистісне самовизначення, професійне самовизначення, професійні цінності, професійний розвиток, педагогічна діяльність.

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